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Research Article

**A STUDY ON ASSESSMENT OF PHYSICAL ACTIVITY AND
ITS ASSOCIATION WITH QUALITY OF LIFE OF
MAINTENANCE HEMODIALYSIS PATIENTS****P. Suriya**Assistant Professor, Dept of Renal Dialysis technology, Grace College of Allied Health Science,
The Tamil Nadu DR.MGR Medical University Chennai-600032.**Abstract:**

The Kidney Disease Improving Global Outcomes (KDIGO) guidelines recommend classification of CKD based on cause, category of glomerular filtration rate (GFR), and albuminuria. The symptoms of worsening kidney are unspecific, and might include feeling generally unwell and experiencing a reduced appetite. Often, chronic kidney disease is diagnosed as a result of screening of people known to be at risk of kidney problems, such as those with high blood pressure or diabetes and those with a blood relative with chronic kidney disease. The assessment of physical activity using pedometer showed that majority of our hemodialysis patients were physically not active. There is no significant association between physical activity and Quality of Life in our hemodialysis patients. We observed an significant association between age and physical activity in our study population. The physical activity decreases with the increasing age of hemodialysis patients ($p < 0.01$).

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INTRODUCTION:**DEFINITION:**

Chronic kidney disease is a progressive irreversible deterioration of renal function due to slow destruction of renal parenchymal cells essentially terminating in death when sufficient number of nephrons have been damaged over a period of months or years.

The Kidney Disease Improving Global Outcomes (KDIGO) guidelines recommend classification of CKD based on cause, category of glomerular filtration rate (GFR), and albuminuria

The symptoms of worsening kidney are unspecific, and might include feeling generally un well and experiencing a reduced appetite. Often, chronic kidney disease is diagnosed as a result of screening of people known to be at risk of kidney problems, such as those with high blood pressure or diabetes and those with a blood relative with chronic kidney disease.

Chronic kidney disease may also be identified when it leads to one of its recognized complications, such as cardiovascular disease, anemia or pericarditis.

CKD is characterized based on five stages, with stage one being the mildest and usually causing few symptoms and stage five being severe illness with

poor life expectancy if untreated. Stage-5 of CKD is also called End stage Renal disease (ESRD).

Adverse outcomes of chronic kidney disease can often be prevented or delayed through early detection and treatment. Earlier stages of chronic kidney disease can be detected through routine laboratory measurements.

- The presence of chronic kidney disease should be established, based on presence of kidney damage and level of kidney function (glomerular filtration rate [GFR]), irrespective of diagnosis.
- Among patients with chronic kidney disease, the stage of disease should be assigned based on the level of kidney function, irrespective of diagnosis, according to the KDQOL CKD classification.

According to KDIGO guidelines CKD is defined by structural or functional abnormalities of the kidney, with or without decreased GFR or GFR <60ml / min/1.732m² for ≥3 months, with or without kidney damage refers to pathologic abnormalities documented by biopsy or imaging, alterations in urinary sediments of proteinuria (proteinuria / creatinuria >200mg/dl, albuminuria / creatinuria > 30mg/dl)

ACCORDING TO KDIGO

STAGES	DESCRIPTION	GFR ml/min/1.732m ²
1.	Damage with normal or increased GFR	>90
2.	Damage with mild decreased GFR	60-89
3(a)	Mild to Moderately decreased GFR	45-59
3(b)	Moderate to severe decreased GFR	30-44
4.	Severe decrease GFR	15-29
5.	Kidney failure	<15

EPIDEMIOLOGY

- Kidney Disease: Improving Global Outcomes (KDIGO) guidelines has substantially contributed to the early detection of different stages of chronic kidney disease (CKD). Several recent studies from different parts of the world mention a CKD prevalence of between 8 and 13%. The number of people receiving chronic RRT (dialysis or kidney transplantation) for kidney failure worldwide has progressively increased over the 50 years since these treatments became available, and this increase continues.

TREATMENT REGIMENS:

- Renal transplantation
- Dialysis

- Hemodialysis
- Peritoneal dialysis

DIALYSIS

Dialysis is the passage of molecules in solution by diffusion across a semi permeable membrane. Essential elements of this process are a solvent containing dissolved solutes and the membrane that contains pores through which some or all of the solutes move by diffusion. Membrane characteristics that determine permeability to a particular solute include the average effective pore size, the number, geometry and distribution of pores within the membrane, membrane surface area, thickness and surface characteristics

HEMODIALYSIS

Hemodialysis is defined as a process of removal of metabolic waste products such as urea, creatinine and excess water from the blood by the principle of diffusion and ultrafiltration through a semipermeable membrane through an artificial kidney in an extracorporeal circuit. Hemodialysis was originally termed extracorporeal dialysis because it was performed outside the body. Several early pioneers laid the foundation for therapeutic dialysis. Graham,

a professor of chemistry in Scotland, invented the fundamental process of separating solutes using semipermeable membranes in vitro and coined the word "dialysis."

Dialysis follows following principles in its working

- Diffusion
- Ultra filtration

COMPLICATIONS OF HEMODIALYSIS:

- Intradialytic hypotension
- Muscle cramps
- Nausea and vomiting
- Dehydration
- Edema
- Xerostomia
- Hyperkalemia
- Metabolic acidosis
- Pruritis
- Anemia
- Headache
- Chest pain
- Back pain
- Itching
- Fever and chills

LIFESTYLE CHANGES IN DIALYSIS PATIENTS:

- Hemodialysis alters the life style of the patient and family and interferes with their lives. The major areas of life affected by ESRD and its treatment includes employment, eating habits, vacation activities, sense of security, self-esteem, social relationships, and the ability to enjoy life .
- Hemodialysis consists a complex procedure for patients that requires frequent hospital or dialysis centers visits, mainly three times a week, thus implying substantial changes in the normal way of patients' living.
- Long-term dialysis therapy itself often results in a loss of freedom, dependence on caregivers, disruption of marital, family, and social life, and reduced or loss of financial income
- Maintenance hemodialysis (MHD) patients frequently experience reduced quality of life (QOL) and have decreased daily physical activity (DPA) and physical performance.
- Due to these reasons, the physical, psychological, socioeconomic, and environmental aspects of life are negatively affected, leading to compromised QOL.
- Also physical inactivity may be worse, due to frequent presence of different comorbidities, such as anemia, uremic neuro and myopathy, bone and mineral disorders,

cardiovascular abnormalities and depression.

ASSESSMENT OF PHYSICAL ACTIVITY AND QUALITY OF LIFE:

- The KDQOL-36™ is a short form that includes the SF-12 as generic core plus the burden of kidney disease, symptoms/problems of kidney disease, and effects of kidney disease
- Daily physical activity can be evaluated more precisely in ESRD patients using pedometer. Physical activity assessed using pedometer has gained popularity because of its simplicity and low cost. Although a pedometer is unable to detect upper body movements, swimming and cycling but walking is the most common form of physical activity.
- The physical activity is a rehabilitation too that should be included in the standard of care for end stage renal disease patients.

Report-based measures include self-report tools and diaries that are designed to provide subjective information about physical activity levels and the context of physical activity behaviors. These measures tend to be the most feasible to use (due to both lower administrative and processing costs) but also tend to have lower validity.

The choice of measurement approach for a given application depends to a great extent on the relative importance of feasibility and validity, but a number of other factors also come into play when selecting a measure.

Figure 5a: Physical Activity Assessment Tools and Their Relative Positions on the Feasibility/Validity Continuum

Monitor-based measures include various devices designed to objectively quantify movement, such as accelerometers, GPS units, and pedometers or devices to measure the intensity and duration of physical activity such as heart rate monitors. These measures have a good balance between feasibility and validity, making them attractive for a number of research and evaluation applications.

Criterion measures include the DLW method, indirect calorimetry, and direct observation. These measures provide criterion estimates of energy expenditure and movement and are typically used for validation studies, smaller applications, or in lab-based study designs where precise indicators are needed.

Figure 5b: Feasibility/Validity Continuum for Physical Activity Behavior

Pedometers are simple devices which measure spontaneous physical activity. Pedometers were successfully used to encourage patients to increase their habitual physical activity through self-monitoring of its intensity. Goal setting of physical activity is well known as one of the most popular techniques to promote it in maintenance hemodialysis patients.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:**USE OF PEDOMETER TO INCREASE PHYSICAL ACTIVITY AMONG CHILDREN AND ADOLESCENTS WITH CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE**

- **Aalia Akber et.al(2014)** has done a study which utilizes an innovative research methodology (to explore the connection between association of change in physical activity with change in 6-min walk distance and health-related quality of life and PF physical function scale of the pediatric quality of life index (PedsQL). The study designed a 12-week pedometer-based intervention among children and adolescents with CKD, including those with non-dialysis dependent CKD (CKD-ND), end-stage renal disease on dialysis, and those with a transplanted kidney. In conclusion, children and adolescents with CKD had low levels of physical activity and did not significantly increase their activity over 12 weeks of a pedometer-based intervention. However, changes in physical activity were associated with changes in physical functioning and performance, and performance increased among those who did increase their activity.

CORRELATES OF HABITUAL PHYSICAL ACTIVITY IN CHRONIC HEMODIALYSIS PATIENTS

- **Sylwia Zamojska et.al(2006)** has done this study. The objective of this study is to assess interdialytic spontaneous physical activity in chronic haemodialysis (HD) patients in relation to their nutritional status, severity of anaemia, inflammation and dialysis adequacy. In this study the patient's daily physical activity was measured during 48 h between mid-week dialysis sessions by pedometers. Nutritional status was estimated by anthropometric methods (BMI and mid-arm muscle circumference) and serum albumin concentration. Additionally, body composition was estimated using a multifrequency phase-sensitive bioimpedance analysis (BIA). Severity of anaemia was determined by blood haemoglobin level and haematocrit value, and the presence of inflammatory state was determined by high sensitivity plasma C-reactive (CRP) protein measurements. In conclusion, the study found that even those chronic dialysis patients who did not report any problems with walking were physically inactive, malnourished and more anemic. Interdialytic physical activity measured by pedometers reflects habitual daily activity and is correlated with nutritional status and the severity of anemia.

ASSOCIATION AMONG SF36 QUALITY OF**LIFE MEASURES AND NUTRITION, HOSPITALIZATION, AND MORTALITY IN HEMODIALYSIS**

- This study is by **Kamyar Kalantar et.al(2001)**. In this study, SF36 was used to evaluate the QoL status in patients on MHD and examined the cross-sectional associations between this instrument and other pertinent clinical and laboratory values, including nutritional status and inflammatory measures. In this study, the score of the SF36, a self-administered questionnaire used to assess QoL, had significant correlations with serum albumin and hemoglobin and a strong association with prospective hospitalization and mortality in patients on MHD. As a conclusion, the study found that the SF36 had a significant positive correlation with both the BMI and the percentage of body fat, as measured by NIR technology, which indicates that overweight outpatients undergoing MHD perceive a worse QoL when compared with less-obese individuals. Han et al. (25) used SF36 to assess the QoL in 4000 healthy individuals and found that large waist circumferences and high BMI are more likely to be associated with impaired quality of life and disability affecting basic activities of daily living. Goller et al. (26) found that, in a group of patients undergoing chronic peritoneal dialysis, where a higher BMI is more frequently present than among patients on MHD, overweight patients had lower SF36 scores and were more impaired in physical functioning.

NEGLECTIBLE IMPACT OF DIFFERENTIAL ITEM FUNCTIONING BETWEEN BLACK AND WHITE DIALYSIS PATIENTS ON THE KIDNEY DISEASE QUALITY OF LIFE 36- ITEM SHORT FORM SURVEY (KDQOLTM-36)

- **Ron D. Hays et.al (2018)** has done this study. The study examined differential item functioning (DIF) of the Kidney Disease Quality of Life 36-item (KDQOLTM-36) Burden of Kidney Disease, Symptoms and Problems with Kidney Disease, and Effects of Kidney Disease scales between Black (n=18,404) and White (n=21,439) dialysis patients. This study examined whether the KDQOL-36, a widely used HRQOL measure among dialysis patients, had equivalent measurement properties between Black and White patients. Since the study found negligible impact of measurement noninvariance on KDQOL-36 factor mean estimation between these groups, substantive comparisons of HRQOL between Black and White dialysis patients can be made using the KDQOL-36. The ability to

make such comparisons is critical for epidemiological surveillance of dialysis patients' health, and to use in interventions to improve HRQOL among dialysis patients.

PHYSICAL ACTIVITY MEASURED BY PEDOMETER IN CHRONIC HEMODIALYSIS PATIENTS

- **Hicham Rafik et.al (2018)** has done this study. The aim of this study is to record physical activity level during seven consecutive days using a pedometer to measure daily step numbers and to determine factors involved in physical activity limitation. Physical activity was recorded using a using a pedometer (model ONWALK 900 multifunction pedometer, GEONAUTE) to measure daily step numbers during seven consecutive days. 43 patients were included. 55, 8 % were men and median age was 53.4 ± 16.4 years. Median time on dialysis was 67 months [25-97]. Median physical activity was 4769 steps / day [1597-8364]. Patients were separated into 2 groups according to daily step numbers: a group < 5000 and a group > 5000. In univariate analysis, patients <5000 were women, older, obese and had lower serum albumin and serum creatinine levels. In multivariate analysis, only age and female sex were significantly associated with sedentary lifestyle. The study concluded that hemodialysis patients present with a very low physical activity level. A higher risk of sedentary was identified in older women.

PHYSICAL ACTIVITY IN HEMODIALYSIS PATIENTS MEASURED BY TRIAXIAL ACCELEROMETER

- **Edimar Pedrosa Gomes, et.a; (2015)** has done this study . The objective of this study was to compare physical activity in daily life in HD patients with control individuals, by using a triaxial accelerometer, and to investigate variables associated with inactivity. Patients were classified as sedentary, somewhat active, or active, based on the numbers of steps taken (<5000, 5000-7499 or >7500 steps/day). The analysis of physical functioning was performed by 6MWT during the non-dialysis day. The SF-36 was used for the evaluation of quality of life In conclusion, HD patients are less active than individuals without chronic kidney disease, especially on dialysis days. These patients should be motivated to enhance the physical activity

PEDOMETER-DETERMINED PHYSICAL ACTIVITY AND INDICATORS OF HEALTH IN

JAPANESE ADULTS

- **Takahiro Mitsui1, et.al (2008)** has done this study. The purpose of this study is to examine the relationship between pedometer-determined physical activity and indicators of health such as BMI, %BF, blood pressure, blood glucose, and blood lipoproteins in the Japanese population. All participants were local residents aged between 48 and 69 years who had a medical check-up at public health center. All measurements were conducted after overnight fasting. A foot-to-foot bioelectrical impedance analyzer was used to measure height, body weight, and %BF. BMI was calculated by dividing weight in kilograms by height in meters squared. Waist circumference was measured at the narrowest part of torso, with the participant standing erect and the abdomen relaxed. Blood pressure was measured using a mercury sphygmomanometer. Blood samples were drawn from a medial cubital vein. The significance of this study is that a clear relationship between pedometer-determined activity and obesity as observed in Caucasian and African-American women was not seen in the Japanese population. In other words, the effects of physical activity on body shape and composition may differ according to race.

PHYSICAL PERFORMANCE, PHYSICAL ACTIVITY AND QUALITY OF LIFE BEFORE AND AFTER KIDNEY TRANSPLANTATION Ryota Matsuzawa .et.al (2018)

Kidney transplantation is generally accepted as the best treatment for patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD). It is, however, unclear whether kidney transplantation improves its decreased physical performance, physical activity and quality of life. A total of 7 consecutive kidney transplant recipients (median age, 45 [25th, 75th percentiles: 23, 72] years; 8 women) were enrolled in this prospective observational study between January 2016 and December 2017. Patient characteristics including age, sex, body mass index, primary cause of kidney disease, smoking habits, comorbidities and laboratory data were collected at baseline. Six-minute walk distance (m) and lower extremity muscle strength (%body weight) were evaluated at before, 3-4 weeks after (hospital discharge), and 2 months after kidney transplantation as measurements of physical performance. Objectively measured physical activity (number of steps [steps/day] and moderate-to-vigorous activity time [min]), quality of life (KDQOL-SF questionnaire) and CKD stage were assessed at before and 2 months after kidney transplantation. The scores of "effect of kidney disease", "burden of kidney disease", and "general

health” in the KDQOL-SF questionnaire were significantly improved after the transplantation, respectively.

However, there were no increase in physical performance and physical activity at between before and 2 months after kidney transplantation. The study concluded that, no improvement of physical performance and physical activity levels was observed in this study. It is noteworthy that physical performance is initially worsened by the major surgical insult, and early renal rehabilitation would be needed for transplant recipients.

COMPARISON OF TWO METHODS TO ASSESS PHYSICAL ACTIVITY PREVALENCE IN CHILDREN: AN OBSERVATIONAL STUDY USING A NATIONALLY REPRESENTATIVE SAMPLE OF SCOTTISH CHILDREN AGED 10–11 YEARS

Paul McCrorie, et.al(2018)

The aim of this study is to describe the objectively measured levels of physical activity (PA) and sedentary time in a nationally representative sample of 10–11-year-old children, and compare adherence estimates to the UK PA guidelines using two approaches to assessing prevalence. To examine these questions, they drew on the SPACES (Studying Physical Activity in Children’s Environments across Scotland) study, the aim of which was to explore the environmental determinants of PA by conducting a large-scale, nationally representative, accelerometry and global positioning systems (GPS) observational study. The data collection for SPACES took place between May 2015 and May 2016. To assess the frequency, intensity and duration of PA, participants who consented to participate in the data collection were provided with a validated accelerometer (ActiGraph GT3X+) and asked to wear the device over eight consecutive days for the waking hours. The study concluded that PA estimates are significantly influenced by the analytical method used to assess prevalence. This could have a substantial impact on the evaluation of interventions, policy objectives and public health investment. Existing guidelines, which focus on daily PA only may not further our understandings about the underlying construct itself. Gender differences exist within this age-group, suggesting greater investment, with particular consideration of seasonality, is needed for targeted intervention work in younger children.

RENAL FUNCTION AND METABOLIC PROFILE IMPROVEMENT AFTER CIRCUIT TRAINING PHYSICAL ACTIVITY AMONG HIV PATIENTS

Elizabeth Daher, et.al(2018)

HIV is a worldwide public health problem and is frequently associated with kidney injury. The aim of this study is to investigate the effect of a physical exercise training on renal function and lipid profile among HIV-infected patients. Patients older than 18 years and using antiretrovirals for at least 36 months were included. They were randomized to either an exercise group (EIG) or a non-exercising control group (CG) for comparative analysis. Anthropometry and laboratory tests were done before and after the 8-weeks period. The study resulted that the majority of patients had low income and complete high school. The initial physical and laboratory data from the control and intervention groups were similar in both groups, except for of BMI levels, which were significantly lower in the EIG ($p < 0.05$). After the intervention there were significant differences in other parameters between the two groups, including body fat, waist circumference, HDL, LDL, triglycerides, urea, glucose and hemoglobin.

The comparison of these parameters before and after the intervention showed mild differences in the control group and significant differences in the intervention group, with improvement in almost all parameters, including renal function (creatinine: 0.9860.1 vs. 0.8560.1mg/dL, before and after, respectively) and metabolic profile, with improvement in glucose, HDL and LDL levels.

AIM AND OBJECTIVE: AIM:

To study the assessment of physical activity and its association with quality of life of maintenance hemodialysis patients.

OBJECTIVES:

- To assess physical activity using pedometer.
- To assess quality of life using KDQOL SF36 questionnaire.
- To study association of physical activity with the quality of life in our study population.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Materials and Methodology:

Sample Area: The study will be conducted at the Department of Nephrology, Grace Hospital and Nursing Home, kaliyakavilai, Kanyakumari district.
Sample Size: 120 patients

Type of the study: Observational Study
Period of the study: 6 months

Inclusion criteria:

- Age 18 – 65 years
- ESRD patients on maintenance Hemodialysis atleast on twice weekly hemodialysis

- Patients who were willing to give informed consent

Exclusion criteria:

- AKI patients
- Amputated Patients
- Bed ridden patients
- Non compliant

Study methodology:

Participants:

Patients with CKD or ESRD were recruited for this study. Males and females ranging from 18-65 years of age with CKD stage 1-4 not yet requiring renal replacement therapy, those undergoing hemodialysis are eligible. We excluded patients who were hospitalized or had initiated with hemodialysis within the prior 3 months and the patients who are amputated and with AKI are excluded. Patients were included in this study after obtaining informed consent and based on their inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Physical Activity:

Physical activity was measured using a GEONAUTE ONWALK 900 pedometer, which was given to each participant. Participants were instructed to clip the pedometer each morning and to wear the pedometer throughout the day while doing usual activities, except sleeping, swimming or bathing. They were asked to remove the pedometer before going to bed and to record the day's step count each night before resetting the device to zero for the next day. After 1 week, the device is been collected from the patients and the average number of steps taken per day over 7 days was calculated.

KDQOL SF36

In this study, we used the SF36 to evaluate the QOL status in MHD. The short form health survey with SF36 questions is a well documented scoring system that has been widely used and validated as a QOL

assessment tool for the general population as well as a standard measure of QOL and as a core component of several major assessment tools, including the kidney disease quality of life survey instrument. In this questionnaire "Physical Component Summary (PCS, 12 items), Symptoms/Problems (12 items); Burden of Kidney Disease (4 items), and Effects of Kidney Disease (8 items)" were assessed.

The purpose of this study is to examine the relationship between pedometer determined physical activity and quality of life in ESRD patients. Patients on maintenance hemodialysis (MHD) experience decreased quality of life (QOL) and significantly greater rates of decreased physical activity. QOL measurements are based on a patient's subjective sense of well-being and are commonly used as an important clinical measure for beneficial extent of medical treatments for patients on MHD. However, the association between this somewhat subjective outcome.

Before and after assessing the physical activity, Quality of Life was evaluated using KDQOL SF36 questionnaire.

Statistical analysis:

The results of the study was analyzed using SPSS software. The data was expressed in percentage, mean & standard deviation. P value <0.05 was considered as statistically significant. ANOVA measures the mean of several groups are all equal or not. The chi-square test and t-test has been done for statistical significant.

Chi-square test was done to assess the categorical variable. The mean of continuous variable were assessed and compared with the other variables using T-test and Anova.

RESULTS:**BASELINE CHARACTERISTICS:****AGE DISTRIBUTION**

In our study there are about 48(42%) patients in the age group of 18-45 years , 67(58%) patients in the age group of 45-65 years .

GENDER DISTRIBUTION

In our study there where 83(72%) males and 32(28%) females.

BODY MASS INDEX:

In our study there were 10(9%) patients with BMI <18.5 , 56(49%) patients with BMI between 18.5-24.99 , 32(28%) patients with BMI between 25-29.99 , 17(15%) patients with BMI >30

BASIC KIDNEY DISEASE:

In our study 63(55%) patients with the basic kidney disease of hypertension , 48(42%) patients had both diabetic mellitus and hypertension , 2(2%) patients had diabetes mellitus , 2(2%) had other BKD of analgesic nephropathy.

VASCULAR ACCESS:

In our study 113(98%) patients had arterio venous fistula as dialysis access, 1(1%) patients had arterio venous graft , 1(1%) patients had central venous catheter as dialysis access.

DIALYSIS VINTAGE:

In our study 62(54%) patients were on dialysis between 12-36 months , 27(24%) patients were on dialysis less than 12 months , 13(11%) patients were on dialysis between 37-60 months, 13(11%) patients were on dialysis more than 60 months

FREQUENCY OF DIALYSIS:

In our study 28 patients (24.3%) were undergoing thrice weekly and 87 patients (75.7%) were undergoing twice weekly dialysis

Kt/V

In this study 34 patients(29.6%) had Kt/V of less than 1.2, 81 patients(70.4%) had Kt/V of greater than 1.2.

AVERAGE NUMBER OF STEPS WALKED PER WEEK:

Among 115 patients , 81(70.4%) patients had physical activity below average, 16 patients had physical activity in average , 18(15.7%) patients had physical activity above average.

Descriptive

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
HEIGHT	115	124	184	158.46	9.11
WEIGHT	115	32	88	62.25	11.99
BMI	115	15.01	71.66	24.8460	6.2171
BSA	115	1.14	2.08	1.6330	.1869
URNE OUTPUT	115	0	1000	343.48	307.90
STEPS WLALED PER WEEK	115	551.28	10578.47	3107.0029	1956.2310
KDQOL SF36					
SF12 – Before	115	13.37	87.50	50.1594	14.2349
SF12 – After	115	24.17	96.67	54.3194	13.5537
BKD – Before	115	.0	75.00	32.3912	16.9570
BKD – After	115	.0	75.00	32.7083	17.2674
SYMPTOMS – Before	115	37.50	100.00	79.8029	11.3054
SYMPTOMS – After	115	23.43	100.00	82.0925	11.3744
EKD – Before	115	21.88	96.88	66.5801	16.8074
EKD – After	115	21.88	96.88	72.4313	14.4564
TOTAL – Before	115	30.97	85.42	62.3545	9.5031
TOTAL – After	115	15.97	86.81	64.8496	9.2962
Valid N (listwise)	115				

KDQOL SF36	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound			
SF12 – Before	< 3500	81	48.320	13.34314	1.48257	45.3705	51.271	13.37	81.2
	3500 - 5000	16	54.984	16.25719	4.06430	46.3218	63.647	30.58	87.5
	> 5000	18	54.143	15.26363	3.59767	46.5535	61.734	33.75	82.0
	Total	11	50.159	14.23497	1.32742	47.5298	52.789	13.37	87.5
SF12 – After	< 3500	81	52.813	13.31601	1.47956	49.8689	55.757	24.17	96.6
	3500 - 5000	16	57.427	13.54483	3.38621	50.2100	64.645	36.67	87.5
	> 5000	18	58.333	14.09350	3.32187	51.3254	65.342	38.75	87.5
	Total	11	54.319	13.55375	1.26389	51.8156	56.823	24.17	96.6
BKD – Before	< 3500	81	30.478	15.79221	1.75469	26.9863	33.970	.0	75.0
	3500 - 5000	16	37.109	19.56144	4.89036	26.6858	47.532	12.50	75.0
	> 5000	18	36.805	18.91944	4.45936	27.3971	46.214	12.50	75.0
	Total	11	32.391	16.95703	1.58125	29.2588	35.523	.0	75.0
BKD – After	< 3500	81	30.635	15.67176	1.74131	27.1700	34.100	.0	75.0
	3500 - 5000	16	38.281	20.26838	5.06710	27.4810	49.081	12.50	75.0
	> 5000	18	37.083	20.27839	4.77966	26.9991	47.167	12.50	75.0
	Total	11	32.708	17.26740	1.61019	29.5186	35.898	.0	75.0
SYMPTOMS - Before	< 3500	81	80.227	10.85483	1.20609	77.8276	82.628	37.50	100.0
	3500 - 5000	16	76.954	12.76281	3.19070	70.1536	83.755	43.75	91.6
	> 5000	18	80.422	12.24671	2.88658	74.3326	86.512	57.50	95.8
	Total	11	79.802	11.30540	1.05423	77.7144	81.891	37.50	100.0
SYMPTOMS - After	< 3500	81	82.004	11.45197	1.27244	79.4720	84.536	23.43	100.0
	3500 - 5000	16	80.970	11.68646	2.92161	74.7434	87.197	50.00	93.8
	> 5000	18	83.487	11.25349	2.65247	77.8910	89.083	58.33	95.8
	Total	11	82.092	11.37444	1.06067	79.9913	84.193	23.43	100.0
EKD – Before	< 3500	81	67.303	16.60203	1.84467	63.6322	70.974	21.88	96.8
	3500 - 5000	16	67.116	16.48619	4.12155	58.3314	75.901	31.25	87.5
	> 5000	18	62.849	18.43788	4.34585	53.6805	72.018	25.00	93.7
	Total	11	66.580	16.80743	1.56730	63.4753	69.684	21.88	96.8
EKD – After	< 3500	81	73.358	13.89263	1.54363	70.2867	76.430	21.88	96.8
	3500 - 5000	16	71.681	15.95347	3.98837	63.1802	80.182	31.25	93.7
	> 5000	18	68.925	15.84262	3.73414	61.0466	76.803	43.75	93.7
	Total	11	72.431	14.45649	1.34807	69.7608	75.101	21.88 4	96.8 0

TOTAL - Before	< 3500	81	61.6931	9.15174	1.01686	59.6695	63.716	30.9	85.4
	3500 - 5000	16	64.4555	11.22822	2.80705	58.4724	70.438	45.6	85.4
	> 5000	18	63.4635	9.62759	2.26924	58.6758	68.251	46.7	78.4
	Total	11	62.3545	9.50317	.88618	60.5990	64.110	30.9	85.4
TOTAL – After	< 3500	81	64.2092	9.58711	1.06523	62.0893	66.329	15.9	86.8
	3500 - 5000	16	66.1519	8.79848	2.19962	61.4636	70.840	49.7	82.6
	> 5000	18	66.5742	8.48491	1.99991	62.3547	70.793	49.0	78.9
	Total	11	64.8496	9.29629	.86688	63.1324	66.566	15.9	86.8

Crosstabs:**ASSOCIATION OF Kt/V WITH WEEKLY AVERAGE OF STEPS WALKED BY THE PATIENTS.****Crosstabulation**

		AVERAGE STEPS			Total
		< 3500	3500 - 5000	> 5000	
KT/V < 1.2	Count	25			3
	% within KT/V	73.5%	5.9%	20.6%	100.0%
KT/V > 1.2	Count	56	14	11	8
	% within KT/V	69.1%	17.3%	13.6%	100.0%
Total	Count	81	16	18	11
	% within KT/V	70.4%	13.9%	15.7%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	3.055	2	.21
Likelihood Ratio	3.410	2	.18
Linear-by-Linear Association	.029	1	.86
N of Valid Cases	11		

a. 1 cells (16.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 4.73.

ASSOCIATION OF AGE WITH WEEKLY AVERAGE OF STEPS WALKED BY THE PATIENTS.**Crosstab**

			AVERAGE STEPS			Total
			< 3500	3500 - 5000	> 5000	
AGE	18 - 45 Years	Count	24	9	15	48
		% within AGE	50.0%	18.8%	31.3%	100.0%
	45 - 65 Years	Count	57	7	18	64
		% within AGE	85.1%	10.4%	4.5%	100.0%
Total		Count	81	16	18	115
		% within AGE	70.4%	13.9%	15.7%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	19.076	2	.00
Likelihood Ratio	19.674	2	.00
Linear-by-Linear Association	18.910	1	.00
N of Valid Cases	11		

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 6.68.

ASSOCIATION OF GENDER WITH WEEKLY AVERAGE OF STEPS WALKED BY THE PATIENTS.**Crosstab**

			AVERAGE STEPS			Total
			< 3500	3500 - 5000	> 5000	
GENDER	Male	Count	55	12	16	83
		% within SEX	66.3%	14.5%	19.3%	100.0%
	Female	Count	26			33
		% within SEX	81.3%	12.5%	6.3%	100.0%
Total		Count	81	16	18	115
		% within SEX	70.4%	13.9%	15.7%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	3.304		.19
Likelihood Ratio	3.77		.15
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.20		.07
N of Valid Cases	11		

- a. 1 cells (16.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 4.45.

ASSOCIATION OF BMI WITH WEEKLY AVERAGE OF STEPS WALKED BY THE PATIENTS.**Crosstab****AVERAGE STEPS**

		< 3500	3500 - 5000	> 5000	Total	
BMI	< 18.50	Count		1		
	% within BMI		50.0%	40.0%	10.0%	100.0%
18.5 - 24.99	Count	39		1		5
% within BMI		69.6%	8.9%	21.4%		
25 - 29.99	Count	23				3
% within BMI		71.9%	18.8%	9.4%		
> = 30	Count	14				1
% within BMI		82.4%	5.9%	11.8%		
Total	Count	81	1	1		11
% within BMI		70.4%	13.9%	15.7%		
		100.0%				

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	10.535	6	.10
Likelihood Ratio	9.296	6	.15
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.857	1	.17
N of Valid Cases	11		

a. 5 cells (41.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.39.

ASSOCIATION OF DIALYSIS VINTAGE WITH WEEKLY AVERAGE OF STEPS WALKED BY THE PATIENTS.

Crosstab

		AVERAGE STEPS			Total
		< 3500	3500 - 5000	> 5000	
DIALYSIS VINTAGE < 12 MONTHS	Count	17	5		2
	% within DIALYSIS VINTAGE	63.0%	18.5%	18.5%	100.0%
12 - 36 MONTHS	Count	45	8		6
	% within DIALYSIS VINTAGE	72.6%	12.9%	14.5%	100.0%
37 - 60 MONTHS	Count	10	2		1
	% within DIALYSIS VINTAGE	76.9%	15.4%	7.7%	100.0%
> 60 MONTHS	Count		1		1
	% within DIALYSIS VINTAGE	69.2%	7.7%	23.1%	100.0%
Total	Count	81	16	18	11
	% within DIALYSIS VINTAGE	70.4%	13.9%	15.7%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	2.351	6	.88
Likelihood Ratio	2.445	6	.87
Linear-by-Linear Association	.115	1	.73
N of Valid Cases	11		

a. 6 cells (50.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.81.

ASSOCIATION OF FREQUENCY OF DIALYSIS WITH WEEKLY AVERAGE OF STEPS WALKED BY THE PATIENTS.

Crosstab

		AVERAGE STEPS			Total
		< 3500	3500 - 5000	> 5000	
FREQUENCY OF DIALYSIS	THRICE WEEKLY	Count 19	5		24
	% within FREQUENCY OF DIALYSIS	67.9%	17.9%	14.3%	100.0%
	TWICE WEEKLY	Count 62	11	1	74
	% within FREQUENCY OF DIALYSIS	71.3%	12.6%	16.1%	100.0%
Total	Count	81	16	1	98
	% within FREQUENCY OF DIALYSIS	70.4%	13.9%	15.7%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	.493	2	.782
Likelihood Ratio	.471	2	.792
Linear-by-Linear Association	.010	1	.922
N of Valid Cases	11		

a. 2 cells (33.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 3.90.

DISCUSSION:

- ❖ In our study 115 CKD patients undergoing maintenance hemodialysis were enrolled and their physical activity and quality of life was assessed.
- ❖ Among 115 patients, 48(41.7%) patients were in the age group of 18-45 years and 67(58.3%) patients were between 45-65yrs.
- ❖ 83(72.2%) patients were male and 32(27.8%) were female.
- ❖ In this study, 10 patients (8.7%) underweight (BMI <18.5), 56(48.7%) patients were with normal weight (BMI 18.5-24.99), 32(27.85%) patients were overweight (BMI 25-29.99), 17 patients (14.8%) were class 1 obesity (BMI >=30).
- ❖ In this study 63(54.8%) patients had the Basic Kidney Disease of Hypertension, 48(41.7%) patients had both Diabetes Mellitus and Hypertension, 2(1.7%) patients had Diabetes Mellitus and 2(1.7%) had analgesic nephropathy.
- ❖ 113(98.3%) patients had Arterio venous fistula, 1(0.9%) patient had Arterio venous graft, 1(0.9%) patient with central venous catheter as a dialysis access.
- ❖ In this study 27(23.5%) patients were on dialysis for less than 12 months, 62(53.9%) patients were on dialysis between 12-36 months , 13(11.3%) patients were on dialysis between 37-60 months and 13(11.3%) patients were on dialysis for more than 60 months of vintage.
- ❖ In study 28 patients (24.3%) were undergoing thrice weekly and 87 patients (75.7%) were undergoing twice weekly dialysis.
- ❖ In this study 34(29.6%) patients had Kt/V of less than 1.2 and 81(70.4%) patients had Kt/V of greater than 1.2.
- ❖ Among 115 patients, 81(70.4%) patients walked less than 3500 steps per week, which is considered as below average; 16(13.9%) patients walked between 3500-5000 steps per week which is considered as average; 18(15.7%) patients walked for greater than 5000 steps per week ; which is considered as above average.
- ❖ In our study population ,
 - Among the age group of 18-45 years, 24(50%) patients walked less than 3500 steps per week ; 15(31.3%) patients walked greater than 5000 steps per week and only 9(18.8%) patients

walked between 3500-5000 steps per week .

- Among the age group of 45-65 years, 57(85.1%) patients walked less than 3500 steps per week ; 7(10.4%) patients walked between 3500-5000 steps per week and only 3 (4.5%) patients walked greater than 5000 steps per week.
- We observed an significant association between age and physical activity in our study population. The physical activity decreases with the increasing age of dialysis patients (p<0.01).

CONCLUSION:

- The assessment of physical activity using pedometer showed that majority of our hemodialysis patients were physically not active.
- There is no significant association between physical activity and Quality of Life in our hemodialysis patients.
- We observed an significant association between age and physical activity in our study population.
- The physical activity decreases with the increasing age of hemodialysis patients (p<0.01).

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APPENDIX
PROFORMA

Patient name:

Age:

Gender:

UHID NO:

Height:

Weight:

BMI:

BSA:

Urine Output:

Basic Kidney Disease:

DIALYSIS DETAILS:

Dialysis Vintage: Frequency of dialysis: Vascular Access:

Kt /V: Ultrafiltration : QOL:

INVESTIGATIONS:

Sodium: Potassium: Urea: BUN:

Creatinine:

	DAY 1	DAY2	DAY 3	DAY 4	DAY 5	DAY 6	DAY 7	TOTAL
STEPS								
TIME								
DISTANCE COVERED								
Kt/v								

KDQOL SF36 QUESTIONNAIRE**Your Health**

This survey includes a wide variety of questions about your health and your life. We are interested in how you feel about each of these issues.

1. In general, would you say your health is: [Mark an in the one box that best describes your answer.]

Excellent	Very good	Good	Fair	Poor
▼	▼	▼	▼	▼
<input type="checkbox"/>				

The following items are about activities you might do during a typical day. **Does your health now limit** you in these activities? If so, how much? [Mark an in a box on each line.]

Yes, limited a lot	Yes, limited a little	No, not limited at all
--------------------------	-----------------------------	------------------------------

2. Moderate activities, such as moving a table, pushing a vacuum cleaner, bowling, or playing golf
3. Climbing several flights of stairs

During the past 4 weeks, have you had any of the following problems with your work or other regular daily activities as a result of your physical health?

Yes	No
▼	▼

4. Accomplished less than you would like..... ₁.....₂

5. Were limited in the kind of work or other activities ₁.....₂

During the past 4 weeks, have you had any of the following problems with your work or other regular daily activities as a result of any emotional problems (such as feeling depressed or anxious)?

Yes	No
▼	▼

6. Accomplished less than you would like..... ₁.....₂

7. Didn't do work or other activities as carefully as usual ₁.....₂

8. During the past 4 weeks, how much did pain interfere with your normal work (including both work outside the home and housework)?

Not at all	A little bit	Moderately	Quite a bit	Extremely
▼	▼	▼	▼	▼
<input type="checkbox"/> ₁	<input type="checkbox"/> ₂	<input type="checkbox"/> ₃	<input type="checkbox"/> ₄	<input type="checkbox"/> ₅

These questions are about how you feel and how things have been with you during the past 4 weeks. For each question, please give the one answer that comes closest to the way you have been feeling.

How much of the time during the past 4 weeks...

		A good			
All	Most	bit	Some	A little	None
of the	of the				
time	time	time	time	time	time
▼	▼	▼	▼	▼	▼

9. Have you felt calm and peaceful?..... 1..... 2..... 3..... 4..... 5..... 6
10. Did you have a lot of energy? 1..... 2..... 3..... 4..... 5..... 6
11. Have you felt downhearted and blue? . 1..... 2..... 3..... 4..... 5..... 6

12. During the past 4 weeks, how much of the time has your physical health or emotional problems interfered with your social activities (like visiting with friends, relatives, etc.)?

All	Most	Some	A little	None
of the				
time	time	time	time	time
▼	▼	▼	▼	▼
<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5

Your Kidney Disease

How true or false is each of the following statements for you?

	Definitely true ▼	Mostly true ▼	Don't know ▼	Mostly false ▼	Definitely false ▼				
13. My kidney disease interferes too much with my life	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
14. Too much of my time is spent dealing with my kidney disease	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
15. I feel frustrated dealing with my kidney disease	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
16. I feel like a burden on my family	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5

During the past 4 weeks, to what extent were you bothered by each of the following?

	Not at all bothered ▼	Somewhat bothered ▼	Moderately bothered ▼	Very much bothered ▼	Extremely bothered ▼
17. Soreness in your muscles?.....	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
18. Chest pain?	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
19. Cramps?	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
20. Itchy skin?.....	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
21. Dry skin?.....	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
22. Shortness of breath?.....	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
23. Faintness or dizziness?.....	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
24. Lack of appetite?...	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
25. Washed out or drained?.....	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
26. Numbness in hands or feet?.....	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
27. Nausea or upset stomach?.....	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
28 ^a . (Hemodialysis patient only)					
Problems with your access site? ...	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
28 ^b . (Peritoneal dialysis patient only)					
Problems with your catheter site?..	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5

Effects of Kidney Disease on Your Daily Life

Some people are bothered by the effects of kidney disease on their daily life, while others are not. How much does kidney disease bother you in each of the following areas?

	Not at all bothered	Somewhat bothered	Moderately bothered	Very much bothered	Extremely bothered
	▼	▼	▼	▼	▼
29. Fluid restriction?....	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
30. Dietary restriction?.	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
31. Your ability to work around the house?	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
32. Your ability to travel?	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
33. Being dependent on doctors and other medical staff?.....	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
34. Stress or worries caused by kidney disease?	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
35. Your sex life?	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5
36. Your personal appearance?	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 5

AGE	SEX	BMI	BK d	VIN	FQ	KT/v	AVG	SF12		BKD		SYMPTOMS		EKD		TOTAL	
2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	59.58	62.9	18.75	18.75	91.7	91.7	78.1	93.75	69.9	74.44
1	1	1	2	2	2	3	2	54.17	62.5	75	75	43.8	50	43.8	59.38	50.7	59.03
2	1	2	3	3	1	2	2	37.08	47.5	18.75	18.75	72.9	81.3	31.3	31.25	45.7	51.94
1	1	3	2	2	2	2	2	70.42	72.1	43.75	43.75	87.5	91.7	81.3	81.25	75.6	77.5
1	1	2	2	1	2	2	3	54.58	61.3	50	50	68.8	70.8	53.1	75	58.5	66.24
1	1	2	2	1	1	2	2	64.58	68.3	37.5	37.5	83.3	83.3	50	59.38	64.6	67.92
1	1	2	2	4	1	1	3	35	38.8	50	50	60.4	58.3	40.6	50	46.7	49.03
1	1	1	2	1	1	3	3	50.42	55.4	50	50	93.2	93.2	25	46.88	58	65.7
2	1	3	1	2	2	2	3	36.67	45.8	37.5	25	62.5	62.5	56.3	53.13	49.7	50.69
2	1	3	3	2	2	2	1	50.45	42.9	31.25	31.25	59.9	87.5	71.9	68.75	66.6	62.22
1	2	4	3	2	1	2	1	46.67	50.9	18.75	18.75	83.3	87.5	75	78.13	62.1	66
2	2	4	2	2	2	2	3	67.92	69.6	31.25	31.25	91.7	91.7	37.5	43.75	65	66.94
2	1	2	2	4	1	2	1	37.5	42.5	31.25	31.25	70.8	75	56.3	62.5	52.1	56.52
1	1	2	2	2	1	2	1	75	96.7	0	0	75	83.3	53.1	53.13	61.8	65.14
2	1	3	3	2	2	2	1	63.33	63.3	25	37.5	77.1	85.4	59.4	59.38	62.8	66.94
2	1	4	2	2	2	1	1	37.5	46.7	43.75	43.75	83.3	85.4	59.4	71.88	58.3	64.86
2	1	3	3	3	1	2	1	20	24.2	12.5	12.5	54.2	57.2	21.9	21.88	31	34.5
1	1	4	2	2	2	2	2	70.84	56.3	56.25	68.75	68.8	89.6	71.9	71.88	85.4	72.22
1	1	2	2	1	2	1	3	78.33	80	18.75	18.75	87.5	91.7	78.1	81.25	74.7	77.36
2	1	2	2	2	2	3	1	49.17	54.1	31.25	31.25	86.4	89.6	34.4	53.13	55.4	63.2
2	1	4	3	2	2	1	1	39.17	51.3	31.25	31.25	83.3	85.4	40.6	50	53.3	60.14
1	1	2	2	2	2	1	3	46.25	47.9	12.5	12.5	91.6	91.6	78.1	81.25	64.7	65.97
1	1	4	2	4	2	1	3	41.67	43.8	37.5	37.5	81.3	85.4	56.3	56.25	57.6	59.72
1	1	1	2	2	2	3	2	32.5	36.7	31.25	31.25	68.8	70.5	43.8	50	46.9	49.74
1	1	2	3	2	2	2	1	52.08	56.3	50	50	100	100	90.6	90.63	76.4	77.78
1	1	2	2	1	2	1	1	64	64.6	12.5	12.5	81.3	81.3	87.5	87.5	69.4	68.75
1	2	3	2	2	2	1	1	35	38.3	56.25	31.25	89.6	89.6	71.9	67.8	63.8	60.99
2	1	2	3	4	2	2	1	47.08	54.2	18.75	18.75	93.8	95.8	62.5	65.63	62.9	66.66
2	2	1	2	4	1	3	2	72.92	47.9	75	75	62.5	72.9	62.5	68.75	67.4	63.89
2	1	3	3	2	2	1	1	49.17	56.7	12.5	12.5	79.2	83.3	78.1	84.38	61.5	66.81
1	1	2	3	2	2	2	1	43.33	46.7	12.5	12.5	83.3	85.4	40.6	46.88	52.6	55.83
2	1	3	3	4	1	2	1	41.25	51.3	25	25	87.1	93.8	56.3	65.63	58.2	65.69
2	1	3	3	2	2	1	1	45.2	45.4	31.25	31.25	81.3	85.4	56.3	71.88	58.2	63.06
2	1	3	2	3	2	2	3	47.5	52.5	18.75	18.75	83.3	87.5	50	56.25	56.8	61.25
1	1	2	2	1	2	1	1	57.08	59.2	43.75	56.25	81.3	81.3	65.6	78.13	65.6	70.42
2	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	58.75	68.8	37.5	37.5	85.4	87.5	78.1	78.13	69.6	72.64
1	1	2	2	1	2	2	3	79.17	81.3	68.75	68.75	70.8	70.8	75	75	75	74.99
2	1	2	2	2	2	1	1	49.17	53.3	25	25	87.3	85.4	78.1	78.13	65.7	66.93
1	1	2	2	1	1	1	3	43.33	50	12.5	12.5	80.5	85.4	81.3	93.75	61.3	67.36
2	1	2	2	4	1	1	1	133.8	24.6	0	0	37.5	52.1	71.9	87.05	33.1	44.99
2	1	3	3	3	2	1	1	38.75	53.8	31.25	31.25	79.2	83.3	68.8	81.23	58.1	67.22
2	1	3	3	3	2	2	1	49.17	54.2	31.25	31.25	86.4	89.6	34.4	53.13	55.4	63.2
2	1	2	1	4	1	2	1	68.75	68.8	50	50	100	100	93.8	96.88	82.6	83.33
2	1	2	3	1	2	1	1	64.58	68.3	37.5	37.5	83.3	83.3	50	59.38	64.6	67.92
2	1	2	3	1	2	1	1	23.33	30	12.5	12.5	79.2	81.3	53.1	65.63	47.4	50.05
2	1	1	2	2	1	2	1	55.83	62.7	12.5	12.5	77.1	81.3	75	87.5	62.4	69.01
2	1	4	3	4	2	1	1	48.75	50.8	37.5	37.5	91.7	81.3	65.6	68.75	65.6	63.47
1	1	3	2	2	2	1	1	62.5	62.5	25	25	77.1	77.1	81.3	81.25	67.4	67.36

1	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	45.42	48.8	25	25	75	81.3	56.3	65.63	55.4	60.69
2	1	3	3	2	1	1	1	34.58	40	18.75	18.75	85.4	87.1	65.6	75	56.7	61.25
1	2	3	2	1	2	2	2	37.92	45	18.75	25	87.5	93.8	68.8	68.75	59.2	63.29
2	1	3	2	2	2	3	1	33.33	34.6	25	25	85.4	85.4	81.3	81.25	60.4	63.38
2	1	2	3	3	2	2	1	53.75	65.4	37.5	37.5	85.4	87.5	59.4	62.5	63.8	69.03
2	1	2	2	1	2	2	1	81.25	81.3	56.25	56.25	95.8	95.8	90.6	96.88	85.4	86.81
1	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	51.67	55	25	25	83.3	89.6	65.6	68.75	63.4	66.24
2	1	3	2	4	2	2	1	50.83	52.5	43.75	43.75	45.8	56.3	96.9	96.88	58.6	62.64
1	1	2	2	2	1	2	1	18.75	40	25	25	87.5	87.5	43.8	43.75	47.9	55.14
1	1	3	3	2	1	2	1	64.58	64.6	12.5	12.5	87.5	87.5	90.6	90.63	72.2	72.22
1	1	2	3	1	2	1	1	50	51.7	50	50	79.2	81.3	68.8	75	63.9	66.52
1	1	2	2	2	2	2	3	82.08	87.5	25	25	91.7	95.8	59.4	59.38	73.9	77.08
2	2	4	3	2	2	2	1	44.17	45.8	12.5	12.5	58.3	68.8	50	65.63	46.7	54.17
2	1	3	3	2	2	1	1	41.67	45	43.74	43.75	85.4	89.6	78.1	78.13	64.6	67.08
1	1	3	4	2	2	1	3	46.67	48.8	75	75	95.8	95.8	90.6	90.63	76	76.21
1	2	2	2	2	2	3	3	57.5	57.5	12.5	12.5	91.7	91.7	65.6	71.88	65.7	67.08
2	1	3	3	2	2	1	1	55	66.7	25	25	89.6	89.6	62.5	75	64.9	71.53
2	1	3	3	2	2	2	2	41.67	43.3	37.5	37.5	85.4	87.5	84.3	87.5	65.3	67.22
2	1	3	3	2	2	1	1	60	75	25	25	75	79.2	68.8	78.13	63.1	71.53
1	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	52	56.7	12.5	12.5	79.2	83.3	78.1	84.38	61.5	66.81
2	1	3	3	2	2	2	1	27.92	32.1	12.5	12.5	66.7	66.7	40.6	43.75	41.9	44.02
1	1	2	3	2	2	2	3	55	55	37.5	37.5	87.5	88.6	68.8	68.75	66.9	67.07
1	1	1	2	2	2	3	1	37.08	37.1	31.25	31.25	79.2	81.3	81.3	84.38	60.3	61.67
2	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	65.83	67.9	25	25	97.9	97.9	90.6	90.63	77.5	78.19
2	1	2	2	3	2	2	1	47.5	57.9	25	25	87.5	85.4	87.5	87.5	67.2	70.5
1	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	68.75	72.9	50	67.5	57.5	83.3	93.8	93.75	78.5	78.98
2	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	80	82.1	25	25	89.5	85.4	78.1	78.13	76.7	15.97
1	2	1	2	2	1	2	1	56.25	54.6	25	25	87.5	89.6	65.6	68.75	61.9	66.11
1	2	2	3	2	1	3	1	44.58	46.3	43.75	43.75	83.3	77.1	78.1	71.88	64.9	61.92
2	1	2	3	4	1	2	1	47.5	47.9	18.75	18.75	85.4	87.5	78.1	78.13	63.8	64.58
2	1	2	3	2	2	2	1	57.5	59.1	12.5	12.75	87.5	89.6	75	78.13	66.4	69.02
2	1	2	2	1	2	2	1	60	66.7	6.25	6.25	60.4	54.2	78.1	87.5	58.2	60.41
2	2	3	2	2	2	2	2	53.33	57.5	12.5	12.5	72.9	72.9	71.9	75	59.4	61.53
1	1	2	2	1	2	2	1	60.42	64.1	62.5	62.5	95.8	95.8	60.7	68.75	72.9	75.86
2	1	2	3	1	2	1	1	46.67	58.3	31.25	31.25	83.3	85.4	75	75	63.5	68.06
1	2	3	2	1	2	2	1	42.08	55.8	31.25	31.25	83.3	85.4	84.4	84.38	64	69.31
2	2	1	3	2	2	3	1	54.17	52.1	56.25	56.25	81.3	85.4	84.4	84.38	70.1	70.83
1	1	3	2	2	1	2	1	67.92	67.1	18.75	18.75	93.8	93.8	68.8	62.5	71.3	69.88
1	2	2	3	1	2	2	1	62.08	63.3	25	25	87.5	85.4	81.3	84.38	70.7	71.11
1	2	2	2	1	2	1	1	45.83	45.8	18.75	18.72	75	75	96.9	96.88	66.9	63.88
2	2	3	2	2	2	2	1	47.5	51.7	50	50	85.4	89.6	71.9	78.13	65.8	70
2	1	4	3	2	2	1	1	43.33	52.5	31.25	31.25	68.8	77.1	50	62.5	51.9	60.55
1	1	3	2	1	2	2	2	60	65.4	31.25	31.25	85.4	83.3	67.7	68.75	67.1	68.33
1	1	2	2	2	2	2	3	50	51.7	50	50	79.2	81.3	68.8	75	63.9	66.52
2	2	2	3	2	1	2	1	57.08	63.8	18.75	18.75	79.2	85.4	78.1	90.63	64.9	71.94
1	2	2	2	1	2	3	1	47.08	53.3	18.75	18.75	87.5	89.6	62.5	62.5	60.8	63.6
2	1	2	3	2	2	2	1	35.83	42.5	18.75	18.75	77.1	83.3	40	62.3	42.1	46.3
1	1	2	2	2	2	1	3	33.75	50.4	25	25	72.7	77.3	74.15	68.75	49.4	60.14
2	1	3	3	1	2	2	1	44.17	45.8	25	25	81.3	85.4	56.3	62	57.1	60.41
2	1	2	3	3	2	1	1	35.83	42.5	18.75	18.75	77.1	83.3	40.6	56.25	48.7	56.53

2	2	4	3	1	2	1	1	47.5	51.7	50	50	85.4	89.6	71.9	78.13	65.8	70
2	2	4	3	3	2	2	1	60.83	62.9	62.5	62.5	75	81.3	65.6	71.88	66.8	70.97
2	2	4	2	3	1	2	1	25	29.2	50	50	77.1	79.2	62.5	71.88	53.5	57.64

1	2	2	3	2	2	3	1	53.75	57.1	75	75	81.3	81.3	78.1	78.13	70.7	71.81
2	2	4	2	2	2	1	1	48.33	42.1	25	25	79.2	85.4	84.4	84.38	64	64.03
2	2	4	3	3	2	2	1	31.25	37.1	25	25	87.5	23.4	22.5	65.63	56.3	58.88
1	2	4	2	2	2	2	1	53.33	57.5	12.5	12.5	72.9	72.9	71.9	75	59.4	61.53
2	2	2	2	2	1	3	1	63.76	65.4	43.75	43.75	77.1	77.1	81.3	84.38	69.9	71.11
2	2	2	3	2	2	2	1	43.33	51.8	50	50	75	75	75	78.13	61.7	65.57
2	1	3	2	3	1	2	2	87.5	87.5	37.5	37.5	89.6	89.6	87.5	87.5	82.6	82.64
2	2	2	3	1	2	2	1	69.58	78.8	56.25	56.25	79.2	81.3	71.9	71.88	71.8	75.55
1	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	47.92	40.4	50	50	66.7	66.7	75	81.25	60.4	59.31
2	2	1	2	4	2	2	1	35.42	35.4	56.25	56.25	62.5	64.3	71.9	81.24	54.9	57.64
2	2	3	2	2	2	1	1	34.58	37.9	18.75	31.25	66.7	68.8	78.1	81.25	53.2	57.08
2	1	4	2	2	2	2	1	38.83	38.3	56.25	56.25	77.1	77.1	75	87.5	61.4	64.16
2	2	4	3	3	1	3	1	46.67	46.7	31.25	31.24	75	75	56.3	62.5	56.5	57.92
2	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	35.5	35.5	31.25	31.25	79.2	83.3	50	56.25	53.8	56.76

BKD	
DM	1
HTN	2
DM/HTN	3
OTHR	4
DIALYSIS VINTAGE	
<1 yr	1
1-2.99	2
3-4.99	3

AGE	
18-45	1
45-65	2

KT/V	
<1.2	1
>1.2	2

AVERAGE		STEPS	
1		<3500	
2		3500-5000	
3		>5000	

BMI	
< 18.5	1
18.5-24.99	2
25-29.99	3
>30	4

FREQUENCYOF DIALYSIS	
thrice weekly	1
twice weekly	2